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Banditry And Socio-Economic Development Of Kaduna State, Nigeria, 2012 - 2022

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ABSTRACT

The paper investigates how banditry has affected socioeconomic development in Kaduna State, Nigeria, from 2012-2022. Banditry has become a pervasive social malady confronting most states in Nigeria. Methodologically, the paper adopts a mixed research method, employing both survey and descriptive techniques. Questionnaires and interviews were utilized as instruments for data collection, with primary and secondary data sourced and applied in the study concurrently. The simple random sampling technique was employed to select participants, resulting in a sample size of four hundred individuals, which was analyzed using descriptive statistics, percentages, and frequency outlines. To provide a theoretical explanation for the surge in banditry, the Queer Ladder theory was adopted as a framework. The paper observes that the causes of banditry in Kaduna State are predominantly linked to the breakdown of political and socioeconomic order. In conclusion, to eliminate banditry and foster socioeconomic development, the paper recommends that the state government embark on a political and socio-economic reorientation of the populace and organize continuous entrepreneurship empowerment initiatives aimed at creating gainful employment, eradicating poverty, and addressing issues of illiteracy.

Keywords: Banditry, Development, Kaduna State, Socioeconomic Development, Mixed Methods, Political Reorientation.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, a country located in West Africa is a federal state with thirty – six state structure and seven hundred and seventy four Local Government Councils. It is also the most populous country in Africa and one of the most endowed in terms of human and natural resources. Its people are heterogeneous and this may have accounted for the plethora of conflicts recorded in the Country. To maintain these people of diversity, the core responsibility of the State therefore is to protect the people's lives and properties. Thus, Egobueze & Okorie (2023) observed that:

Security of lives and properties of citizen is the primary responsibility of the State. The citizens would see the State as irresponsible if this is not achieved because they believe that their protection is a fundamental right, which is not to be treated with levity. This accounts for why most modern States have enshrined this in their constitutions or Acts of Parliament. Nigeria as a sovereign State is not an exception (p.286).

Security of lives and properties of the citizens of every nation is the primary responsibility of the State and that is the core essence of governance and that engenders developmental endeavour to all the

emerging and already settled nations. Banditry, due to the lapses in the security and development activities in most African states became the new emerging reality. This emerging reality of having banditry as recurrent security threat became so apparent that most scholars became focused on trying to study the patterning and the root of this menace called banditry. Both contemporary and historical African history illustrate a profound connection between international politics and banditry.

The menace of banditry has also like of most of the other countries in Africa, found its way into the Nigerian landscape. Several Nigerian scholars have posited diverse reasons to the advent of the banditry in Nigeria. While some believe that the obvious lapses in the security configuration of the national defence apparatus was so lapse and lacking in so many features of what the ideal standard is expected to be like (Nwaoburu, 2023). Olaniyan and Yahaya (2016) are of the opinion that the concentration of all the security apparatus at the federal level has given rise to the fledging nature of banditry in the country. They believe that the security apparatus should be decentralized in order to be able to carry out a wide spread coverage of expected necessary outcomes. The power, command and control should not only rest with the masters at the federal capital. The states and the regions should also be fully empowered to carry out security activities and account for the movements in their areas. This form of empowerment of the regional and state powers is very key because, the regional and state leaders are the people on the ground, who also know all their nooks and crannies very well, as against the present structure of handing everything bordering on security into the hands of the President who stays at the federal capital. Others have diverse opinion to the cause of banditry.

From the stand point of Suleiman (2017) as well as Mustapha (2019) argued the various institutions of the state are very frail in their modus operandi thereby making their institutional outcome to be vulnerable in nature. The areas along the borders are not well policed and as a result, creating space for lapses and idle manifestations at the long run. People from the neighbouring countries can come into the country through many areas that are unattended to. The borders remain wide open for all forms of infiltration. They included, sham leadership, corruption, unemployment and other forms of failures that are apparent in the Nigerian nation as part of the reasons why banditry took foothold in the country. Certain vices arise from the ongoing power struggle initiated by individuals seeking to assert their dominance over the population. These vices include militancy, counter-protests, protests, killings, kidnappings, and violent agitations, all of which contribute to the escalation of banditry in current society.

Other scholars like Egbueze (2021) said that the present practice in Nigeria is such that a particular ethnic group dominates the political and economic control in the clear exclusion of the others. Even at the areas where the hub of economic activities such as Oil and Gas originate from. This is so much felt by the owners of the land and sea areas where the exploitation of these mineral resources originate from, that the people from those areas are not accorded their due recognition in the scheme of things such as infrastructural development, employment, adequate compensation for the loss of use of their lands as well as adequate clean-up and remediation of their environment whenever there are spills arising from the oil and gas activities by the firms involved in the exploitation. As far as that feeling of exclusivity of the other regions, especially the regions that suffer the brunt of the adverse effects of explorations by those organizations contracted by the Nigerian state still persist, the people of the hinterlands of the Niger Delta areas would find justification to looking for alternative means of making their feelings felt by the powers at the central echelon of leadership and one of those ways that some of the people resorted to was to resist what they termed as massive usurpation of their resources under their feet.

Most of them resorted to kidnapping, abduction, attacks of the pipelines and flowlines that carry the oil and gas from one end to the other. Some out of this dissatisfaction resorted to blowing up the pipelines, carting away of the well heads, Christmas trees, reservoirs and well locations thereby causing massive disruptions to the free flow of the products that the nation depended upon for their much needed revenue. The people felt that while the particular ethnic group controls the federal level as well as the security agencies, the federating units are left impoverished and that their areas that produce the wealth of the nation are among the neglected areas and that whenever they complained, they were molested by the security forces that were still at the beck and call of the ethnic groups in leadership either killing or

injuring their people during protests, so the best for them would be to look for ways to draw the attention of the people to their plights by resorting to destruction of the infrastructures used for the said exploitation. Some resorted to armed resistance as they faced the security agents and this resorted to several deaths from both sides. As a result of all these activities, militancy began to come up in many of the Niger Delta states. As a result of anger in the minds of the people, either in form of discontentment due to the concentration of the proceeds and wealth accruing from their areas into the hands of the tribes they regarded as usurping their natural resources or as a result of lack of employment, absence of infrastructural and human development in the face of financial resources enjoyed by only those in authority, the resort to resistance through carrying of arms and ammunition was not a good development to the overall development of a modern society.

The widely held opinion is that the infiltration of the aliens that trooped out of the other African sub-regional entities where armed skirmishes had already ensued was the major result of the prevalence of banditry in the West African regions including Nigeria. To the extent of this truth, it is also worthy to note that the resistance to the seeming exploitation by a group of persons as well as the cases of pastoral and farming communal crises are among the major causes of the advent of banditry in Nigeria (Egobueze (2021). From the submission of Kwaja (2013) cited by Mohammed and Jibrin (2016) describing banditry in Northern Nigeria, it says thus:

Rural banditry associated with cattle rustling has become a major concern for public policy in contemporary Nigeria. It refers to the practice of stealing cattle and animals from herders, or the raiding of cattle from the ranches. Although driven by different needs and factors, it is increasingly an economically-based form of criminality perpetuated by informal networks. Rural banditry thrives as a means of 'primitive' accumulation of cowherds in the context of subsistence and commercial pastoralism. The most disturbing effect of this banditry is the unsettling of pastoralist transhumant activities. Furthermore, rural banditry is accompanied by rape, kidnapping, organized attacks on villages and communities, and looting (p.15).

This is a true summation of the present situation in the northern part of the country. At the moment, the menace of banditry has covered both the North-Eastern and North-Western parts of the entire northern Nigeria. States like Bornu, Yobe and Adamawa areas have seen a lot of disruptions to human lives and other forms of vices as the people cannot freely go to their normal businesses. The farmers, especially women cannot go to their farms without been abducted and while the mothers or the elderly ones are placed on payment of ransoms before releasing them or killed, the younger women are placed as sex slaves or forcefully married to themselves in their own ways without the proper parental consent.

This worrisome development of banditry is also very much applicable to the North-Western areas of Nigeria. States like Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna states are among the hotbeds of this prevailing menace. A lot of people have been killed as a result. Cattle rustling is on the increase as well as the daily occurrence of the farmers and Herdsmen crises. Several forms of peace moves have been made to placate the criminals by the government of those states but none of the moves has succeeded. The tempo of banditry is very high around the areas. A lot of clashes claim lives and properties of the contending parties. Thus, this paper has two key objectives, as follows; to:

1. Ascertain the causes of banditry in Kaduna State.
2. Examine the nexus between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Queer Ladder Theory

The study also adopts Queer Ladder Theory (QLT) as its theoretical frameworks. The theory was propounded by Daniel Bell; an American Sociologist. The theorist came up with the theory in a bid to explain source of organized crime in the society. This theoretical underpinning has gained wide and contemporary recognition as a viable postulation to explain organized crime and crime studies. The theorist stated that organized crime steer up in the society due to the eagerness means for socio-economic

empowerment and social height. The theory assumes that; organized crimes are behavioural instruments, hence, a constructed means to an end; it is a method of social uplifting and achieves socioeconomic enhancement; and also a means of making money and build affluence (Okoli & Orinya, 2013).

Another fundamental assumption of the Queer Ladder Theory is that organized crime foster in a situation or place where the presence of governance is at its barest minimal, and deplorable state of security and policing; high level of corruption; and poverty and socioeconomic depression are rife (Nwoye, 2000; Lyman, 2007). Under such condition, the propensity and tendency for people to engage in organized crime tend to be high because there is no strong institution against criminality. Invariably, the consequence of engaging in organized crime is proportionally lower than the rate of benefits of organized crime (Okoli & Orinya, 2013). Okoli and Agada, (2014) reiterating on the Queer Ladder Theory stated that organized crimes is an ultimate means to generating material wealth and skyrocket social recognition. The authors see such organized crimes as consciously planned toward a specific objective. They also believe that organized crime can be considered to be a drive to achieving relevance and attention among the social group or targeted at the economic potentials of a society. Odoma and Akor, (2019); Okoli and Agada, (2014) posit that organized crime is a scheme to generate wealth and acquire power. The key factor of this theory rest on the postulation that organized crime can only thrive where the government is not organized, with little or no access to favourable living condition; where there are no strong socioeconomic infrastructures.

This theory is one of the most suitable theories that helps to explain the prevalence of banditry in the Northwest part of Nigeria especially Kaduna State. From the tenet of the theory which states that individual's crime actions are deliberate and instrumental and also organized crime is a scheme to generate wealth and acquire power, could be used to explain the actions of bandits which is deliberate because they know the consequence of their action, as they carry out actions that are extremely unlawful and inhumane, such as kidnapping, raiding communities, farmlands and cow-pillaging. These actions are done in states and communities in the North with little or no presence of government and security, as well as socioeconomic depression, just to achieve material wealth. The bandits in recent times have employed the courage of attacking state institutions and personnel in a bid to gain social relevance and attention. Mustapha (2019) echoed the insecurity in Northwest Nigeria is chiefly motivated by criminal propensity to generate economic wealth especially banditry.

The enabling environment for such high rate of banditry in the Northwest is driven by socio-economic wants of the people and crumbling standard of living in the state. This is happening so well because the government have failed in their responsibility in ensuring security. Hence, those who climb the social ladder with organized crime, such banditry, do so as a conscious instrument of accumulating economic incentives and socio-economic benefits (Okoli & Orinya, 2013).

AN APPRAISAL OF BANDITRY AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN KADUNA STATE

Banditry is linked to insecurity. Some scholars like Igbuzor (2011) and Oche (2001) while conceptualizing security placed emphasis on the absence of threats to peace, stability, national cohesion, political and socio-economic objectives of a country. It is conceived as to be secure and free from both fear of physical, psychological abuse, violence, persecution, or death and from want such as food, health and good job (Asmau & Abdurashed, 2020). Also, Omede (2012) sees security as a dynamic condition which involves the relative ability of a state to counter threats to its core values and interests.

Security can further be described as stability and continuity of livelihood (stable and steady income), predictability of daily life (knowing what to expect), protection from crime (feeling safe), and freedom from psychological harm (safety or protection from emotional stress which results from the assurance or knowing that one is wanted, accepted, loved and protected in one's community or neighbourhood and by people around (Nwanegbo & Odigbo, 2013). It also focuses on emotional and psychological sense of belonging to a social group which can offer one protection. This description of the foregoing structured the concept of security into four dimensions. These dimensions can be woven together to give a

composite definition of security as the protection against all forms of harm whether physical, economic or psychological (Olabanji & Ese, 2014).

Adegbami (2013) posited that one of the fundamental human rights of the people in any given state is the right to security and this is why it is always provided for in the constitution of most sovereign states. Nigeria is not an exception, thus Section 14 (2) (b) of the Nigerian 1999 constitution states clearly that “the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of the government”. Although the problem of insecurity is not new in Nigeria, however since the confirmation of Goodluck Jonathan in February 2010 as the President and Commander-in-Chief of Armed Forces of the Federal Republic of Nigeria following the hospitalization and eventual death of President Yar’adua, the nation has been witnessing unparalleled security challenges. Now, hardly a day goes by without a report of one security challenge or the other. Unfortunately, ordinary citizens as well as the nation’s economic resources are at the receiving end of this wanton destruction.

Nigeria security has been quite tense and volatile in the northwest due to the alarming rate of banditry with the attendant massive plundering and carnage, which has plunged the region into a state of insecurity in all spheres of life. Thus, Omoyibo and Akpomera (2012) avowed that security in Nigeria is synonymous to an individual who put iron bars across his or her windows which eventually prevents the individual from escaping a fire outbreak. For them, the only condition for the maintenance of peace and the guarantee of security is by upholding law and order. By this, state could be secured against threats which may include low-level civil disorder, crime, organized violence, or even an armed insurgency (El-Rufai, 2012).

Adegbami (2013) opined that insecurity as a bane to human survival and economic squalor in Nigeria. The scholar was of the view that there is a link between survival and security. The relationship between these two concepts is interrelated, as one cannot thrive without the other. Citizens cannot survive without the basic condition of security. Thus, security is the quality of freedom from danger, fear and doubt among others that the people enjoy.

Olapeju and Adeniyi (2021) argued that banditry is not a new phenomenon, in fact, the act of banditry is part and parcel with the culture of life in the North, but the difference is since the arrival of the Fourth Republic, banditry has evolved into a terrorist group that out of the constant resistance from the herdsmen to protect their cattle with small arms and light weapon, the bandits took up arms too to be able to carry out their nefarious act. The community which they live in has also mobilized local security that carries small arms and light weapons also to protect their farms and properties from these bandits. The authors blamed arm proliferation for the reason why bandits now parade with weapons. This is coupled with the Boko Haram insurgency that exposed most of these organized criminals with ammunitions and other harmful weapons. Corruption, low socioeconomic infrastructure, poor security and loosed borders have widened the scope of organized crime perpetrators in the Northwest. The views above was also conversed The concept of banditry has been metamorphosing over the years, through social changes and circumstances. A person termed ‘bandit’ connotes a freedom fighter in the early 19th century around some part Europe and Americas. At that point it is used to describe someone who is an activist for social and political freedom, fighting against social discrimination of the bourgeois on the serfs or against unlawful imperial colonist (Warto, 1994, cited in Olapeju & Adeniyi, 2021). Robinson (2009) revealed that bandits such as Herachio Bernel, Chucho el Rotoand Santanon were revered as nationalists who fought for Mexican independence. Contrary to this, as much as the Mexicans revered these bandits as nationalist, the government from time considered them as criminals (Watts, 1987, cited in Olapeju & Adeniyi, 2021).

Therefore, the social status of these bandits began to evolve from nationalist to agents of destruction. Therefore, in some societies, the people consider bandits totally different from the government, while the people see those freedom fighters; the government declares them as outlaws, hoodlums and miscreants. However, in the African conventional setting they are viewed differently from the Western climes when it comes to what they consider as banditry. Accordingly, (Curott & Fink, 2008) states that banditry is

viewed with high resentment and proscription, as bandits engage in armed robbery and other related organized crimes.

In the same vein, Rufai (2018) posits that the act of banditry in Africa connotes maiming, killing and destruction of property, which has a correlation to the culture of cattle rustling in Africa. Banditry sparked so much concern in Africa due to the adverse relationship herdsmen and bandits. The herdsmen were the victims of early attacks of bandits who took serious interest in cow pillaging and raiding of farms. Thus, these herdsmen took along lethal weapons, as measures to protect their cattle from bandits attack, hence, in return, bandits took up weapons in a bid to scare and pillage cows comfortably (Addo, 2006). Hence, the use of weapons during pillaging is what is today known as cattle rustling and armed banditry (Murtala, 2018)

Similarly, Adeolu & Oluyemi (2012) noted that the failure of successive administrations in Nigeria to address the challenges of poverty bedeviling the nation has made life burdensome and only the fittest survive. In concurrence with Adebayo (2018) perception, Adeolu, (2018) cited by Adebayo (2018) noted that Nigeria has overtaken India as the country with the largest number of people living in extreme poverty, with an estimated 87 million Nigerians, or around half of the country's population, estimated to be living on less than \$1.90 a day. Alao, Atere and Alao (2015) linked banditry, terrorism and other criminal acts to poverty. Although not all forms of criminal acts could be linked to poverty, it has been contended that economic deprivation influences people to resort to illegal means of meeting their daily needs. It was discovered that because of the attractive benefits accruing from banditry activity, most people, especially the youths tend to join the bandit gangs in the Northwest of Nigeria (Epron, 2014; Adegoke, 2019).

Another driving factor of banditry in northwestern Nigeria worthy of mentioning is the issue of arms proliferation. There has been an incremental influx of small arms and light weapons (SALWs) into Nigeria from the Sahel since the fall of Ghadaffi's regime in Libya (Gaye, 2018). These arms and weapons end up in the hands of non-state actors like terrorists, militants and bandits, who use them to terrorize individuals and communities.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

360 questionnaires were correctly filled and validated, out of the 400 questionnaire distributed while 40 questionnaire were rendered void due to errors made by the respondents. Below are the results of the questionnaire and interviews administered and conducted:

Ascertaining the causes of banditry in Kaduna State:

Banditry emerged as the new threat to security in Nigeria, enlisting a growing list of other organized crimes in the country such as Boko Haram, cultists, herdsmen, kidnappers and militants. In the North central to North west from Kaduna to Zamfara, banditry boost as the current mystery that have carried out huge number of undisclosed carnage. It boils down to the weak policies of the Federal Government that appear to only bother for the people in times of elections (Odinkalu, 2018).

According to Odinkalu, 2018 (2018), banditry is a relative term in Nigeria used to describe different kind of outlawry. In the society, the term is used to define two issues – “ineffective law enforcement in Southern Nigeria and the crisis of ungoverned spaces in Northern Nigeria” (p.1). Before Nigeria's emancipation, governments have had to battle these two kinds of banditry trends. The evidence over time suggests a link between governance, its failures, and banditry.

In present day Nigeria, according to Stephen Ellis, the history of organized crime in Nigeria can be tracked down to organized crimes that took place after independence. He stated as cited by Odinkalu, 2018 (2018) that “shortly before the civil war, when government broke down in some parts of the Western Region and there was a blurred line between political violence, crime, and organized insurgency.” (p.2). Post war analysis revealed that the military regime of Yakubu Gowon could not organize a proper demobilization. As a result of this failed demobilization the civil and

military combatants that lost their positions to the war returned to their respective communities with nothing but weapons and ammunitions, outlawry began to emerge.

In Southern Nigeria, rural and urban banditry still take place but not to compare to the North. Early manifestation of banditry in Southern Nigeria was armed robbery and burglary (Odinkalu, 2018). A popular example is the renowned armed robber known as the “the Doctor” who terrorized and attacked major parts of Lagos just after the Civil War. Due to the terror exacted by these early bandits the military government decreed ultimate death by firing squad for armed robbery. This decree led to the first stringent policy against armed and organized crime in Nigeria. In 1971, firing execution took place against armed robbers in Lagos bar beach (Odinkalu, 2018).

Banditry was not only exclusive to Southern Nigeria. In 1970, the North also suffered early form of armed robbery, with major bank robbery in Kano making away with £27,750. The increased in armed robbery led to the increase of public executions with over 400 armed robbers been executed publicly by firing squad in the North and the South in 1976 (Odinkalu, 2018). Major-General Muhammadu Buhari region from 1984 ordered over 338 public executions. From the regime of Muhammadu Buhari from 1998 to 1996, the number of armed robbery did not only increase but it also metamorphosed into different form of organized crime such as trafficking, kidnapping, burglary and other form of social vices emerged as a formation of banditry in Nigeria (Odinkalu, 2018).

The study is poised to expose the cause of banditry in Kaduna State. The study tends to reveal what led to banditry in the State. Hence, in achieving this objective the study raised the following interrogation:

Research Question 1: *What were the causes of banditry in Kaduna State between 2011-2021:*

Fig. 4.2.1: **Banditry is a house-hold crime in Kaduna State.**

Source: Data from field survey, 2022.

As shown above, it is obvious from the responses of the respondents that banditry is not a house-hold crime in Kaduna State. A business man in Kaduna State; Malam Hussein Ismail in an interview conducted respondent when asked the security situation in Kaduna State in the past ten years stated thus:

The security situation in Kaduna State has been up and down. Not stable (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a local government worker, Abdulmalik Umar responded when asked the same question who stated that: The security situation has become very worrisome (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a public servant in Kaduna State; Maishanu Fatima responded when asked same question stated that:

The security situation has gradually deteriorated from car-snatching to targeted kidnapers, for ransom by miscreants and now to kidnappings by religious insurgents along the Kaduna-Abuja highway and railways (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In the same vein, Mallam Haruna Sule; a public servant responded on the same question stating that: The security situation in Kaduna State until the last 5 years with the arrival of bandits who blocked interstate roads and kidnapped people (Personal communication, July 9, 2022)

Fig. 4.2.1: Responses on some of the factors that caused the prevalence of banditry in Kaduna State

Source: Data from field survey, 2022.

As shown above, it can be deduced that the major factors that have stirred banditry in Kaduna State has been lack of implementation of government policies and promises and the lack of employment of the citizenry. In an interview with Mallam Haruna Sule; a public servant also responding to the question of the state of socio-economic development in Kaduna State in the past ten years, he narrated that:

The state has witnessed growth in terms of business activities with the introduction of many major companies employing thousands of people like the

fertilizer and animal feed factories. The multiple construction sites have also employed thousands (Personal communication, July 9, 2022)

In another interview conducted with a public servant in Kaduna State; Maishanu Fatima responded when asked same question stated that:

The socio-economic indices have been plummeting just like the rest of the country; however the current government has made great strides in overhauling educational sector and infrastructure. It has also made strides in decongesting the major city of Kaduna to reduce rural/urban migration by creating new mega cities around the state (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a local government worker; Abdulmalik Umar responded when asked the same question stated that: The state of socio-economic development in Kaduna State has been affected by insecurity in the past ten years (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In the same vein, a business man in Kaduna State; Malam Hussein Ismail in an interview conducted responded when asked the same question stated thus: The state of socio-economic development in Kaduna State is not growing the way it is supposed to be(Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

Examining the nexus between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State, between 2010-2021

Kaduna State is situated in the heart of North-central Nigeria, adjacent to the Kaduna River, serving as a vital connection to the River Niger. During the era of British colonial rule, Kaduna State emerged as a key focal point in Northern Nigeria, with development initiatives commencing in 1913 with the construction of the Lagos-Kano Railway. By the 1950s, Kaduna had evolved into a central hub for industrial, commercial, and financial activities within the Northern region of Nigeria. Notably, the Nigerian Stock Exchange stands as a prominent financial institution in the area. The southern part of Kaduna State is home to various industries situated along the banks of the Kaduna River, in close proximity to the main railway junction. Among these industries, the cotton-textile spinning and weaving mills play a significant role, producing high-quality fabrics.

Kaduna State boasts a diverse array of industries, ranging from the production of beverages, baked goods, beer, non-alcoholic beverages, and processed meats, to the manufacturing of light goods such as plastic and rubber items, leather goods, ceramics, pharmaceuticals, furniture, and home appliances. Moreover, it serves as a prominent hub in the North for companies specializing in printing and publishing. In addition to these lighter industries, the State is home to enterprises engaged in heavy production, including the manufacturing of steel and aluminum products, electrical components, asbestos cement, concrete blocks, ordnance, and explosives. Furthermore, the State hosts facilities for grinding and melting metals, rolling steel, automobile dismantling and assembly, as well as an oil refinery. Throughout the 1980s, there was a noticeable decline in petrochemical plant activity in the State, while construction and building material industries began to emerge. Agricultural outputs in the State include cotton, hides and skins, shea nuts, and peanuts, with rural areas specializing in the cultivation of sorghum, millet, maize, kola nuts, goats, poultry, and cattle.

Kaduna State is the home of top academic institutions, in fact, the slogan of the State which reads “Centre of Learning” is derived from the reason that it houses some of the renowned academic learning institutions in the country such as the Kaduna Polytechnic College created in 1968, Ahmedu Bello University (ABU), created in 1962, the Nigerian Defense Academy created in 1964, Kaduna State University in 2004; The Nigerian Research Institute for Trypanosomiasis created in 1961 and the National Eye Centre (Britannia, n.d). It is the centre for renowned religious institutions like the Christian teacher-training colleges, as well as research and monumental institutions such as the Nigerian Geological Survey Agency and the Geology Museum. The State also houses the National Museum which is one of the most significant tourist sites in Nigeria featuring exhibitions and beautiful fossils portraying the culture of the Northern Nigerian states. Kaduna State owns a racecourse and the Ahmadu Bello Stadium

created in 1964. Kaduna State is one of the States that link the longest railways that run through the North to the Southern part of Nigeria (Britannia, n.d).

Unfortunately, this rich and prosperous State is now facing issues of insecurity that has rendered most of these industries and factories incapacitated and unable to make profit over the years. Banditry has become the leading insecurity faced by the State, claiming thousands of lives, rendering thousands homeless and destroyed businesses (Britannia, n,d). The study is poised to know how the nexus between banditry and socioeconomic activities in Kaduna State. The study tends to expose the nature of the relationship shared between banditry and socioeconomic factors in the State. Hence, in achieving this objective the study raised the following interrogation:

Research Question 2: *What is the nexus between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State, between 2011-2021?*

Fig. Kaduna State has socio-economic institutions, organizations and infrastructures

Source: Data from field survey, 2022.

The state of the legislature has been identified as the strongest predictors on the survival of every democratic development (Okoosi-Simbine, 2010). Legislature serves as essential constituent for any democratic government and major factor in its sustenance. Its existence predates the advent of modern democracy. It has been noted that the emergence of the legislature dates back to the twelve century and a product of medieval European civilization transformed in the age of democracy to suit the needs of contemporary political systems (Loewenberg 1995).

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As shown above, it is obvious from the responses of the respondents that Kaduna State has socioeconomic infrastructures. In line with the assertion, the respondents asserted that the socioeconomic infrastructures in Kaduna State include: Transportation, Energy, Health, Education, Agriculture, Sports, Entertainment, and Small and Medium Business. In an interview with Mallam Haruna Sule; a public servant also responding to the question of the sources of socio-economic development in Kaduna State, he narrated that: The sources are plenty; employment is key, good road network, many factories, construction sites and blossoming creative industry among youths (Personal communication, July 9, 2022)

On the part of Maishanu Fatima, a Kaduna public servant, in her response as part of the interview, posited that: Revamped educational sector, infrastructural development, provision of enabling environment for small scale industries (Personal communication, July 10, 2022)

A local government worker; Abdulmalik Umar in another interview, responded when asked the same question, stating that: The stability of all parameters of development in the state (Personal communication, 10th July 2022).

Fig. 4.3.2: **The socio-economic infrastructures and institutions in Kaduna State are not strong, hence, ineffective between 2011-2021.**

Source: Data from field survey, 2022

As shown above, it is obvious from the responses of the respondents that Kaduna State within the years under review has weak and ineffective socioeconomic infrastructures.

In an interview with Mallam Haruna Sule; a public servant also responding to the question of how insecurity has affected the socio-economic development in Kaduna State, he narrated that: Development cannot result from insecurity (Personal communication, July 9, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a public servant in Kaduna State; Maishanu Fatima responded when asked same question stated that:

Insecurity has reduced investors from outside the state to come into Kaduna, those that were there are leaving. Major road construction works by federal government

have stopped completely or significantly slowed down (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a local government worker; Abdulmalik Umar responded when asked the same question stated that: Insecurity has exposed vulnerability to the socio-economic development in the state (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In the same vein, a business man in Kaduna State; Malam Hussein Ismail in an interview conducted responded when asked the same question stated thus: Insecurity is not good and does not encourage development. Stable security is preferable for the citizens (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

Fig.4.3.3: There is a nexus between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State, between 2011-2021

Source: Data from field survey, 2022

As shown above, the responses of the respondents reveal that there is a nexus between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State. This therefore, means that banditry has a resultant effect on socioeconomic development in Kaduna. In an interview with a business man in Kaduna State; Malam Hussein Ismail in an interview conducted respondent when asked the nexus between insecurity and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State stated thus: They are connected, they related. No security, no stability in the socio-economic wellbeing (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a local government worker; Abdulmalik Umar responded when asked the same question stated that: The nexus is that they are interwoven. Insecurity fuels a drop to the socio-economic wellbeing of the state (Personal communication, July 10, 2022)

In another interview conducted with a public servant in Kaduna State; Maishanu Fatima responded when asked same question stated that: They are connected, but the influx of insurgents and also their collaboration with known Fulani bandits to execute major attacks has added another dimension to it (Personal communication, July 10, 2022)

In an interview with Mallam Haruna Sule; a public servant also responding to the same question narrated that: All company has closed on account of insecurity but fear has restricted interstate movement (Personal communication, July 9, 2022).

Fig. 4.2.3: Kaduna State socioeconomic infrastructures and institutions need peace and security consolidation.

Source: Data from field survey, 2022.

As shown above, it is obvious from the responses of the respondents that Kaduna State socioeconomic infrastructures and institutions need peace and security consolidation. This is because the study has already established that there is a link between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State. Hence, peace and security would definitely bring development to socioeconomic infrastructure in Kaduna State. In an interview with Mallam Haruna Sule; a public servant also responding to the question of the how can security engender socio-economic development in Kaduna State, he narrated that: Stable security will create less engagement to the Police and military and this means the funds will be rerouted to development. Businesses will grow and employment will be easier (Personal communication, July 9, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a public servant in Kaduna State; Maishanu Fatima responded when asked same question stated that: Stable security will attract investors into Kaduna State from other locations in Nigeria and also the foreigners (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a local government worker; Abdulmalik Umar responded when asked the same question stated that: A secured state will encourage development organizations to operate in the state because they will be secured (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In the same vein, a business man in Kaduna State; Malam Hussein Ismail in an interview conducted responded when asked the same question stated thus: Stable security will create less stress to the Police and the military. Business will grow and employment will come in (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

Fig.4.2.4: Eradicating insecurity and banditry would consolidate socioeconomic development in Kaduna State.

Source: Data from field survey, 2022.

As shown above, the responses of the respondents prove that Kaduna State can consolidate socioeconomic development by eradicating insecurity and banditry. In an interview with a business man in Kaduna State; Malam Hussein Ismail in an interview conducted respondent when asked the causes of insecurity in Kaduna State stated thus:

The cause of insecurity is the infiltration of some unemployed youths from neighbouring States into Kaduna State (Personal communication, July 10, 2022).

In another interview conducted with a local government worker; Abdulmalik Umar responded when asked the same question stated that: The causes is mainly due to failure of State security apparatus (Personal communication, July 10, 2022)

In another interview conducted with a public servant in Kaduna State; Maishanu Fatima responded when asked same question stated that:

The cause of insecurity could be poor quality education, the large number of young population that are unemployed, degradation of moral values in families attributable to failure of enforcement of law and order (Personal communication, July 10, 2022)

In an interview with Mallam Haruna Sule; a public servant also responding to the same question narrated that: This can be adduced primarily to banditry, and drug abuse (Personal communication, July 9, 2022)

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Ascertaining the causes of banditry in Kaduna State, between 2011-2021

The study in its first objective focused on generating the cause of banditry in Kaduna State. Banditry has been the most challenging issue affecting Kaduna State in all ramifications. Out of the 400 questionnaire issued to the respondents, 360 questionnaire were retrieved and used to form the findings for the study on the causes of banditry in Kaduna State. Fig. 4.2.1 revealed that 23% agreed that banditry is a home grown crime while 77% disagreed that banditry is a home grown crime in Kaduna State. This means that banditry is not a crime that generated from the life and activities of the people of Kaduna State. It is apparently a phenomenon that has nothing to do with the way of life of the people but factors of both government and non-state actors could be the reasons for banditry. In fig. 4.2.2 answers the questions of the cause of banditry in Kaduna State.

Out of the 400 questionnaire distributed to the respondents, 360 responses was used to answer the question on some of the factors that have caused the prevalence of banditry in Kaduna State. 6% of the respondents believe that religious factors are responsible for the prevalence of banditry in Kaduna State. 12% blamed fear factors as the cause of banditry in Kaduna State, 9% blamed lack of financial autonomy, 24% blamed the lack of implementation of government policies as the cause of the prevalence of banditry in Kaduna while 35% blamed lack of employment as the cause of banditry in the State. Thus, this means that the cause of banditry in Kaduna State is the lack of the will power of the government to implement its policies and high rate of unemployment of youths.

Examining the nexus between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State:

After generating the causes of banditry in Kaduna State, the study went on asking the link between banditry and socioeconomic development. Over the years, Kaduna State has been regarded as the centre of learning because it boost of the centre for most giant academic institutions in the North is situated in the North central. Besides the centre of learning, it is also the hub centre where most economic and industrials activities take place in the North due to the fact that it was the capital of the Northern part of Nigeria before independence. Hence, most of the architect and image of the riches and prowess of the North was embedded in Kaduna State.

Unfortunately, due to the prevalence of banditry in the State, attacking and destroying state and private organizations even communities, the state is grappling to save socioeconomic development. This therefore is critical to the study to identify the link between banditry and socioeconomic development. Fig. 4.3.1 revealed that Kaduna State have socioeconomic infrastructures, institutions, organizations and infrastructures, with 84% of the respondents agreeing to this assertion, while 16% disagreed to it. The respondents highlighted these infrastructures and institutions into health, education, sport, entertainment, agriculture, transportation, industries and small and medium businesses. Fig. 4.3.2 revealed that the socioeconomic infrastructures and institutions in Kaduna State are not strong and ineffective, with 80% agreeing to this assertion while 20% of the respondents disagreed with this assertion.

This translate that Kaduna State has numerous rich and prosperous socioeconomic institutions but this infrastructures and institutions are not strong anymore and ineffective. Fig. 4.3.3 revealed that there is a nexus between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State, with 76% of the respondents agreeing and 24% of the respondents disagreed to it. Hence, the relationship that exist banditry and socioeconomic development is a mutual link in which one can impact negatively and positively on the other vice versa. Fig. 4.3.4 revealed that Kaduna State socioeconomic infrastructures and institutions need peace and security consolidation, with 80% of the respondents agreeing to this assertion and 20% disagreed to this assertion. Fig. 4.3.5 revealed that eradicating insecurity and banditry would consolidate socioeconomic development in Kaduna State, with 75% of the respondents agreeing to this assertion, while 25% of this disagreed to this assertion. This means that ensuring security and eradicating the surge of banditry in Kaduna State would bring improved socioeconomic development to Kaduna State

In conclusion, the study found that:

- i) The cause of banditry in Kaduna State is multifaceted; mostly due to the breakdown of political, social, economic, cultural and geographical factors;
- ii) The nexus that exist between banditry and socioeconomic development is mutual in the menace and activities of banditry have a causal effect on socioeconomic development, as well socioeconomic factors have influenced insecurity in Kaduna State;

CONCLUSION

This paper discusses the impact of banditry on socio-economic development in Kaduna State, with focus on the causes of banditry in Kaduna State and the nexus between banditry and socio-economic development. Banditry has affected all ramifications of Nigeria's political affairs but its economic and social potentials have been greatly devastated especially in the North central and the North West. The very sacred commandment given to a responsible government is to guide and protect the lives and property of the people. Government formed out of the social contrast reached by the state to give its holistic power and authority to a legitimate group of people to act and govern on their behalf. On this ground, the people have given their trust, confidence, lives and property to this group of people (government). Hence, government is constitutionally bound and empowered with the resources of the state's human and natural resources to guide and protect the lives, business, institutions and organizations of the state and its people.

When the people began to exact violence, mayhem and catastrophe by killing and kidnapping the people and requesting for ransom, destroying the business and properties of the people that have socially contracted the government with massive human and natural resources, then, the government has failed on their part of the social contract to put together the human and natural resources given to them into proper use or utilize this factors to engender peace and stability in the society. The study found that the causes of banditry in Kaduna State between 2011-2021, were multifaceted, mainly due to the breakdown of political, socio-economic and geographical order in Kaduna State. Hence, the study recommended that the state and federal government must look deep internally into the socioeconomic life of the people in a bid to create jobs and ameliorate poverty and improve education and other avenues to increase youth employment and skill development in Kaduna State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. **The amendment of Section 214 of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria:** Section 214 of the constitution that provides for the establishment of the Nigeria Police Force enshrines the centralization of policing responsibility within the control of the federal government. Decentralized policing into a shared responsibility of the state would optimally give the state the instrument to dispatch sufficient policing on the nooks and cranny of the state, conveniently with quick response. Succinctly, this would give rise to the real essence of community-focused policing system sophisticated enough to fully arm and secure the state.
2. **De-radicalization of the people and the creation of entrepreneurship schemes:** The study was able to reveal that there is a nexus between banditry and socioeconomic development in Kaduna State. These nexus includes poverty and unemployment which have left the people no choice but to imbibe criminal tendencies as the surest means to their sustenance. Therefore, over the years these tendencies have bred banditry due to their geographical terrain and opportunities that they can capitalize on. The de-radicalization programme should go hand in hand with entrepreneurship empowerment of the people. This is so because the Hausa people are naturally industrious and have the zeal in crafts and skills such as shoe making, shoes cobbling, tailoring and other artisanal skills. They are so traders and business inclined especially inter-state supplies of goods and services. The government can aid and empower the people with the knowledge and finance to foster these craft and artisanship and enable them shun banditry.

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